

Microfinance for everyone.

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Abstract

1. Introduction

The Global Decentralized Peer to Peer Microfinance Platform, Replacing Intermediaries with Blockchain Technology.

Author biography

Mr. Didier Bosman Bosman Is CEO of ASSESTREAM.

March 1, 2019